

IMPROVED TRANSDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE
FOR EFFECTIVE ECOSYSTEM-BASED
MARITIME SPATIAL PLANNING AND
CONSERVATION IN EUROPEAN SEAS

Deliverable D7.3 Second Annual Report

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MARINEPLAN PROJECT SUMMARY

The diversity of terrestrial and marine life is dramatically affected by human interventions including climate change. Compelling and growing evidence shows that biodiversity underpins ecosystem functions and services, and consequently, human benefits depend on them. Thus, the importance of ecosystems in a good state cannot be underestimated and calls for an effective management of marine activities and sustainable use of marine and coastal resources.

Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) is the main governance process that ideally balances economic, ecological and socio-cultural goals through the regulation of human uses at sea. As a future-oriented process, MSP is well-placed to realise sustainable marine futures. With global and regional conservation and green energy targets ahead, there is an urgent need to define pathways for a better alignment of MSP and systematic conservation planning, as part of the operationalisation of an Ecosystem-Based approach to MSP (EB-MSP).

The EU-funded MarinePlan project supports the implementation of EB-MSP through the development of a Decision Support System (DSS). It will offer guidance for an improved alignment of MSP, spatial conservation, and restoration interventions during the challenging times of ever-increasing pressures on marine ecosystems.

This main goal will be achieved through four specific objectives for the European seas:

- #1 Co-develop with stakeholders the conceptual elements of the DSS (guidelines and tools) and derive best practice guidance for EB-MSP implementation.
- #2 Develop quantitative metrics to operationalise Ecologically or Biologically Significant marine Area (EBSA) criteria and their application at various spatio-temporal scales.
- #3 Implement and apply the DSS based on objectives #1 and #2, its guidelines, metrics, and tools at Planning Sites representing the diversity of European marine areas.
- #4 Provide recommendations and improvements concerning the shortcomings, impediments to, and opportunities of prevailing governance processes to enhance the implementation of EB-MSP.

MarinePlan develops and applies the EB-MSP DSS within seven Work Packages and eight European Planning Sites. The Planning Sites range from coastal ecosystems to open ocean and the deep sea and from local to transboundary scales. Applying and validating the DSS incorporates realistic planning scenarios, key action points to achieve the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and policy recommendations on how to enhance EB-MSP implementation in European Seas. MarinePlan will communicate results to decision-makers at horizontal (between sectors) and vertical (from local to European) levels and enable the transfer of knowledge to areas in differing socio-ecological settings. The improved natural and social science base will ensure effective policymaking to support a greater coherence in implementing environmental policies as well as to enable streamlined planning for marine industries.

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1 AIM OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable reports the main activities and achievements of MarinePlan in months 13 through 24 of the project (10/2023 – 09/2024). It gives an overview over the main events, achievements and publications. The aim is to inform stakeholders and funders about the project’s progress.

1.1 CONTRIBUTORS

Table 1. Names and roles of contributors to this deliverable.

Name	Affiliation	WP Lead	Task Lead
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2 INTRODUCTION & MAIN EVENTS

MarinePlan started officially on the 1st of October 2022 and will run until the 30th of September 2025. A consortium of 17 partners from the EU, UK and Canada have been working together over the past 24 months to improve transdisciplinary science for effective ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning and conservation in European Seas. MarinePlan has developed several EB-MSP tools, and is already applying the EB-MSP DSS within seven Work Packages and eight European Planning Sites. During the second year of the project (months 12-24) we have been focusing on maintaining our solid foundation of internal communication and frequent exchange between partners, and working towards fulfilling MarinePlan's objectives of co-development with stakeholders, developing quantitative metrics and tools, and implementing and applying the DSS at the different Planning Sites.

The second PS Workshop was held in May 2024 in Thessaloniki where the Planning Site team gathered with the main goals of refining the connectivity concepts and links between WP2 and WP3, and fostering exchange between the Planning Sites and Work Packages. They also got a first look at the EB-MSP Assessment tool developed by WP1.

In September 2024, partners from all eight Planning Sites, the seven WPs, as well as several Advisory Board members gathered online and in-person in San Sebastian, Spain for the 2nd General Assembly Meeting. Here, the 40 participants gave updates and progress reports on their respective planning sites and work packages. Connections between the WPs, PSs, and our main objectives were further pinpointed, and a clearer and the path forward to the end of the project was illuminated. Work packages are coming closer together to achieve tool development, refinement, and implementation at the various Planning Sites, deciding how best to move forward with intricate and sometimes delicate relationships between stakeholders, policy holders, and conservationists at the Planning Sites, and how MarinePlan can influence and advise policy on multiple levels.

*Participants of the MarinePlan 2nd General Assembly Meeting
in San Sebastian, September 2024.*

3 MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS BY WORK PACKAGE

Work Package 1: EB-MSP knowledge and guidance

Work Package 1 is on schedule with the development of their Tasks, and up until now, six of the seven Milestones for WP1 have been achieved. In the last 12 months, M1.5 and M1.6 have been met, and the remaining Milestone 1.7: Internal workshop with MarinePlan Planning Sites leaders to get final feedback and lessons learnt on the implementation of the EB-MSP framework, is scheduled to be met in January of next year. The Deliverable 1.1: Operational process template to support the practical implementation of EB-MSP, was also delivered within the past year, and was fundamental for the development and completion of the EB-MSP Assessment Tool showcased at the MarinePlan 2nd General Assembly Meeting in September, 2024.

The development of the EB-MSP Assessment Tool progressed in the past 12 months after a high-level stakeholder meeting was held online in December 2023, where hindrances to the EB-MSP implementation were identified and recommendations given. Application and testing of the EB-MSP assessment framework was also carried out via an online assessment with competent authorities of national MSPs in a transboundary region (France in November and December 2023, and Spain in December 2023). Following suggestions provided by the partners at the Planning Site Meeting in Thessaloniki, Greece (May 2024), the Assessment Tool has also been updated and improved. The EB-MSP Assessment Tool is the operationalization of the EB-MSP assessment framework into a web-based decision support tool, which is interactive and downloadable. The developed tool was presented to all attendees of the 2nd GA Meeting where the different functionalities of the app were shown.

Figure 1: Homepage of the EB-MSP Assessment Tool shown to participants at the 2nd GA Meeting.

Users provide some general information about their MSP processes, such as the implementation and revision time, and the presence of areas of protection, conservation, and/or restoration. Then they answer questions about different tasks or actions and their relevance grouped into different stages of the MSP process and by relevant EB-MSP topics. Users are able to see different types of downloadable graphs and tables produced by the decision support tool (DST). For example, some results are shown as aggregated data in the form of stacked bars, and other results are summarized in radar plots. The graphs provide information on four semi-quantitative fields: implementation degree, relevance, knowledge base supporting the task or action, and the confidence of the respondents. The results obtained in the Bay of Biscay transboundary case were presented at the 2nd General Assembly Meeting as an example.

Figure 2. Assessment and comparison of national MSP Processes. Example of interactive graphs and tables of assessment results by MSP stages.

The EB-MSP Assessment Tool was presented at the ICES Annual Science Conference 2024 (September 2024 in Gateshead, UK), and at the EU-MSP Week (October 2024 in Marseille, France) under the MarinePlan project. Other plans for dissemination include a publication (currently under review with the peer-reviewed, open-access, scientific journal Communications in Earth and Environment), translating the tool into different languages and looking into implementing it in other countries.

With regards to the EB-MSP assessment framework, each Planning Site will continue to : (i) work closely with MSP practitioners, national focal points or MSP competent authorities of their respective PS, (ii) invite them to complete the assessment (PowerPoints with context about the MarinePlan project and its objectives, as well as the EB-MSP assessment framework will be provided for information), (iii) schedule interviews and assist with filling in the EB-MSP assessment with the practitioners/authorities (provide further guidance and explanations if needed), and (iv) feedback given to participating practitioners after data is analysed and results and graphs are ready. After receiving their results, each PS will contrast them with their national MSP competent authorities.

All of the above-mentioned steps taken and progress made towards the development and implementation of the tools relate directly to Objective 3 of the MarinePlan project.

Work Package 2: Science-based EBSA and MPA network design

Work Package 2 has completed all the Milestones set, and has delivered two of the three deliverables outlined in their work package. Deliverable 2.3: Report on physical connectivity between areas of significant ecological value, is currently in progress. Spatially explicit, quantitative measures of three out of the seven EBSA criteria (biological productivity, biological diversity, and naturalness) have been established, the necessary data collected for the Planning Sites, and mapped over space, and where available, also over time. Connectivity matrices as well as EBSA matrices have been developed, and will be made available to WP3.

In line with their Objectives and Task 2.3, WP2 has developed and refined two different modelling approaches which focus on connectivity analyses. The 3D and 2D drift models will be applied with a different focus on connectivity. The 3D approach covers realistic conditions where vertical movement is critical (such as in deeper waters) and focuses on source and sink areas, whereas the simpler 2D approach investigates the long-term temporal variability in horizontal transport by ocean currents. The

connectivity analyses will be fitted to the specific requirements of each planning site and also depend on data availability in the different Planning Sites. Case-by-case meetings will be scheduled to negotiate planning site needs, computational feasibility, and tool-related requirements. Both modelling approaches provide tailor-made connectivity data that can be used by the R-software packages developed in WP3.

Work Package 3: Prioritisation tools and scenario development

Progress has been made during months 12-24 of the MarinePlan project in the tasks set out for Work Package 3. Systematic reviews are underway, analysing current knowledge on systematic conservation planning and restoration, as are scoping reviews of several papers in preparation for a manuscript to be submitted by the end of 2024. Three workshops were held to address Task 3.2: Developing MarinePlan decision tools for integrated planning and prioritization of sites in EB-MSP. The first workshop (in November 2023) consisted of experts on systematic conservation planning, and resulted in a position paper. The second workshop (in December 2023) consisted of policy makers, conservation managers and high-level stakeholders, where WP3 received feedback from conservation stakeholders. And lastly, the third workshop (held in January 2024) saw stakeholders, policy makers, experts on marine restoration and MSP experts come together, and could possibly result in an opinion paper. Both Milestones set for WP3 have already been achieved. Deliverables 3.1 and 3.2 are also already delivered, and D3.3 is in progress.

Over the past 12 months, WP3 has also developed several new tools in keeping with Task 3.2 and Objective 3 of the MarinePlan Project.

A new 3D Planning Tool provides a more holistic 3D perspective, and was developed after a dedicated workshop with over 40 participants took place in February 2024, and then implemented in the Planning Sites in July 2024. A methodology paper titled ‘prior3D: An R Package for three-dimensional conservation prioritization’ was published in Ecological Modelling and a second paper comparing implementation results across all PSs is currently being reviewed by involved partners.

Figure 3. Example of developed and optimized 3D planning code in R, from the 3D Planning Tool.

WP 3 has also developed a Connectivity Tool: Community Detection, which also spurred a dedicated workshop of over 50 participants (June 2024), and which was made available to the consortium for feedback the same month. A methodology paper under this theme titled ‘Spatial Conservation

Planning: Proposing Clustering Methods to Improve Connectivity Protection' is in press in the *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* journal, with a second paper to follow.

Another tool developed and in the preliminary stages of testing is the Coastal Fishing Pressure Index. WP 3 has collected preliminary results for the FPI at the Greek Seas Planning Site, and have a workshop planned for October 2024. Several other tools are in development and will look at ecological corridors, multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) for OECMs, and marine heatwaves.

Work Package 4: Policy advice and stakeholder engagement

In Work Package 4, collected documents and interview transcripts pertaining to Task 4.2: Assessing the adaptive capacity of existing governance regime, were thematically analysed and informed D4.2 and other WP4 publications. WP4 would also like to host a T4.2 Policy Transfer workshop and invite MarinePlan sister projects (such as MARBEFES, MSP4BIO, GES4SEAS) to attend. This workshop will enable the findings on governance problems (T4.2) and identified possible solutions (T4.3) to be presented. The first Milestone of WP4 has already been reached, and the second two Milestones (Policy Roundtable and Backcasting Workshop) will be reached in the last 12 months of the project. It was decided that hosting the Policy Roundtable event in person at the final MarinePlan Meeting in 2025 would enable both EU and national policy makers to attend. Deliverables 4.1, 4.2, and 4.4 are completed, with D4.2 delivered in September 2024. Deliverable 4.2: Report on the barriers to adopting novel and dynamic approaches to MPA designation and implementation, presents an analysis of the adaptive capacity of each PS governance system, and was informed by an analysis of the collected reports and documents and interview transcripts associated with T4.1. The findings demonstrate each PS's key governance obstacles, what/how change is advocated for, and to what extent change has occurred. Deliverable 4.3 is in progress and should be ready by March 2025.

Work Package 5: Planning Sites and Communication

All of the Milestones for WP 5 have been reached, and Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 have also been completed. Task 5.3: Testing and refining tools, concepts and scenarios, is in progress with much work already done in the past 12 months: the WP1 EB-MSP Assessment Tool was tested with stakeholders in France and Spain, and the last Planning Site Meeting was held in Thessaloniki, Greece in May 2024, with the main goals to refine the connectivity concepts and links between WP2 and WP3, and to foster exchange between the Planning Sites and Work Packages. Deliverable 5.1, synthesizing results across PSs concerning EB-MSP and SCP status and obstacles, was submitted in April 2024. The deliverable was revised according to the recommendations made by the reviewers at/after the project's review meeting in May 2024, and resubmitted October 2024. It has been discussed that a paper will be written from D5.1, detailing potential gaps in current EB-MSP practices as well as pathways of integrating EB-MSP and SCP (see Figure 4). D5.2 is in progress, and is set to be finished in M36, incorporating the work done from tasks 5.3 and 5.4

Figure 4. EB-MSP Checklist results by topic and Planning Site, WP5.

It was decided at the 2nd General Assembly Meeting that the next Planning Site Meeting will be held April 8-10, 2025 in Hamburg Germany.

Work Package 6: Data Management and visualisation tools for EB-MSP

The tasks in WP6 are open until the end of the project, with updates, revisions and additions being made throughout the life of the MarinePlan project. Milestones 6.1-6.3 have been reached, and M6.4 and 6.5 are in progress, with some training courses extending past deadlines due to demand. Deliverable 6.1 was submitted and revised as per the review report following the reviewers' recommendations and resubmitted October 2024. The revisions entail making the Data Management Plan (DMP) more concise and more comprehensive, providing a detailed workflow for collecting and archiving datasets, interacting with external data repositories, and accessing hard-to-obtain datasets. It also provides clear guidelines on managing the open access production of reports, datasets, and scientific articles. D6.1 was resubmitted under the title 'Preliminary Data Management Plan'. The new DMP will be designated as D6.5, with its delivery date moved up to better support the Consortium throughout the duration of MarinePlan. Deliverables 6.2-6.4 are still in progress.

Work Package 7: Project Management and Dissemination

The tasks (T7.1 - T7.3) are completed, but are continuously being updated. In accordance with Task 7.1, for example, WP7 is continually and frequently exchanging information with our sister projects as well as other outside projects, organizing meetings and workshops (i.e., joint conferences and/or presentations), and maintaining internal reporting throughout the duration of the project. (NOTE: specific conferences, workshops, and communication and dissemination accomplishments can be found in Table 5.1, Appendix 1, below). Under T7.2, WP7 is continuously maintaining our internal and external communication tools (e.g., SharePoint for internal sharing and joint work on documents, pCould for data sharing, Zenodo community as the project repository, and updated templates for meeting minutes, presentations, etc.).

Dissemination of MarinePlan for Task 7.3 is also ongoing, with our social media and online presence kept up to date, as well as developing new material for all partners to use (flyers, posters, etc.). All

Milestones apart from the last one, M7.8: Final Symposium, have been reached for WP7, and all but the last deliverable have been provided (D7.2: Annual Report, within the last 12 months).

The 18-Month Technical report was also delivered between month 12-24, and reported activities from 01/10/2022 to 31/03/2024. Feedback was given by reviewers, and recommendations and comments were taken into consideration. Work Package 7 in coordination with Work Package 5 will implement the changes suggested by the reviewers, and try to increase dissemination actions targeting civil society at the Planning Sites.

Figure 5: Linkages between expected outcomes, deliverables, tasks and objectives; checked circles indicate completed, a green arrow indicates progress, and a black line indicates not started yet.

3.1 SIGNIFICANT DEVIATIONS IN THE DELIVERY AND TIMING OF MILESTONES AND DELIVERABLES

Deliverable 5.1 was dependent on the development of D1.1 and the respective assessments of the planning sites. We wanted to base D5.1 on the almost final draft of the EB-MSP assessment (D1.1) which caused a delay of D5.1.

Although the Data Management Plan (DMP) was established prior to month 4, the delay of D6.1 was caused by administrative hurdles in establishing the data management infrastructure, which needed describing in the deliverable.

Deliverable 7.1 and 7.2 were delivered delayed but without impact on the progress and achievement of other tasks, activities, and outcomes. Deviations in timing were due to coordination/project management activities demanding more effort than expected, limiting capacities available for other tasks of WP7 during this reporting period.

3.2 DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION & COMMUNICATION (DEC) MEASURES

In Table 3.2 we show the progress made during the past 24 months, by providing the status of the different success indicator measures, which correspond to the defined Dissemination & Exploitation & Communication (DEC) measures.

Table 3.2: Status assessment of the defined success indicators and measures which correspond to the defined Dissemination & Exploitation & Communication (DEC) measures.

Target group / Audience	Channels, tools and materials used and timeframe / regularity (How?) and Measure of success	Timeframe for completion	Total target	Achievement after 24 months	Objective(s) fulfilled
General public	Project website	ongoing	1	Done; www.marineplan.eu	
General public	Short introductory videos	beginning of project	few	Pending; ongoing discussions about story lines/cost-benefits	
General public	Podcasts	beginning of project, regular	10	Pending; Postponed due to capacity limitations & questions about impact/relevance	
General public	Social media	ongoing		ongoing X/Twitter posts; 326 followers by month 24	
General public	Press releases	beginning of project, regular	3	Azores news contribution of MarinePlan annual meeting: https://www.rtp.pt/play/p56/e716215/telejornal-acores ; start 15:06 min	
General public	Project flyer(s)	beginning of project	1	Decided against flyer for sustainability reasons and made a poster and a roll-up banner to present the project	
General public	Newsletters	regular	6	Postponed due to capacity limitations	
General public	Newspaper/magazine articles	regular, conclusion and summary	3	Pending; planned as soon as relevant results are achieved	
Scientific community (research and education)	Peer-reviewed publications	regular	20+	14 published, 2 submitted, 5 in preparation	1-4
Scientific community (research and education)	Presentations at EU and international symposia and conferences	regular	10	35 presentations	1-4
Scientific community (research and education)	Public Deliverable Reports	regular	15	11 (will be published as soon as approved by EU)	1-4

Scientific community (research and education)	Workshops/Trainings	regular	3	7 hosted, 6 contributed/participated	1-3
Scientific community (research and education)	The approach of peer review by appropriate scientific communities will ensure quality standards	regular		Ongoing for all scientific publications	
Scientific community (research and education)	The website will provide links to publications, reports etc.	regular		Ongoing; www.marineplan.eu	
Scientific community (research and education)	Final project symposium	conclusion and summary	1 (100+ attendees)	n.a.; planning started	1-4
Policy makers & NGOs	Reports, policy briefs & “factsheets” detailing the trade-offs between incentives, job creation, regulations and resources conservation needs	regular, conclusion and summary	11	Under discussion	4
Policy makers & NGOs	Website summaries of key MarinePlan research linked to specific policy areas	conclusion and summary		n.a.	4
Policy makers & NGOs	Direct input to national, regional, European and international advisory bodies, including ICES, GFCM, STECF, FAO, OSPAR and HELCOM	regular		Participation in workshops, conferences and including representatives in events of the project - WP3 high level stakeholder workshops	
Policy makers & NGOs	Descriptions of Planning Site scenarios demonstrating improved MPA spatial models and EB-MSP options	regular, conclusion and summary	8	D5.1, D1.1: are the foundations for the scenario development	
Policy makers & NGOs	Policy roundtable with policymakers from across	conclusion and summary	1	n.a.	

	the EU to co-develop MSP recommendations				
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Articles in industry magazines and on websites	regular	2		
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Specific pages on the project website	ongoing			Links to technical reports and publications are provided on the website
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Stakeholder engagement workshops (online and in person) per Planning Site	regular	24 (3x8 PS)		Ongoing regular meetings with stakeholders; For examples the Bay of Biscay: Workshop for D1.1
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Specific information material designed to present relevant MarinePlan results refined for each site with opportunities for feedback and co-development	regular			Each PS will use the general MarinePlan templates to present project results; further general findings are continuously updated in a general project presentation
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	EB-MSP DSS with best practice guidance	conclusion and summary	1		In preparation; see WP1
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Operational EBSA criteria for MPA designation	conclusion and summary			In preparation; see WP2
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Regionalised runs of drift models	conclusion and summary			In preparation; see WP2
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Spatial optimisation tools	conclusion and summary			In preparation: see WP3

policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Visualisation tools to analyse trade-offs	conclusion and summary		In preparation: see WP1, WP3; WP6 (OceanViz)
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Training courses (physical and web-based) at Planning Sites specific tools and training for the EB-MSP DSS provided for each Planning Site	regular, conclusion and summary	3	WP3: 5 Workshops completed

4 PUBLICATIONS

Bas, M., Ortega Cerdà, M., Castro Cadenas, M. D., Lloret Lloret, E., Steenbeek, J., Ramírez Benítez, F., ... & Coll, M. (2024). Impactos acumulativos y planificación marítima. Los proyectos GES4SEAS y MARINEPLAN. Primeros resultados.

<https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/358206>

McAteer, B., & Flannery, W. (2024). Network governance and reflexivity in fisheries management: a case study of Northern Ireland. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 1–13.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2024.2395860>

Vigo, M., Hermoso, V., Navarro, J., Sala-Coromina, J., Company, J. B., & Giakoumi, S. (2024). Dynamic marine spatial planning for conservation and fisheries benefits. *Fish and Fisheries*, 00, 1–17.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12830>

5 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

During months 12-24 of the MarinePlan project, much has happened in the way of communicating and disseminating the project and our achievements. Audiences include research communities, industry and business partners, innovators, EU institutions, national, regional, and local authorities, civil society, citizens, specific end user communities, international authorities (such as the UN, OECD, etc.), and investors. Communication and dissemination included activities such as giving talks and presentations (e.g., at conferences or conventions) about the MarinePlan project and our objectives, poster presentations, further education and training (e.g., lectures or seminars), and social media activities such as posts on X and involvement with the scientific community online.

All of these activities, including details on time and place, type of dissemination, target audience, and more, can be found in Table 5.1, in Appendix 1.

Some partners have also taken on MSc or PhD students to fulfil human capacity building activities. These activities are also included in Table 5.1, Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1

Table 5.1. MarinePlan Dissemination and Communication Activities from 10/2023 until 09/2024.

<u>Lead Participating Organization</u>	<u>Type of Activity</u>	<u>Type of Action</u>	<u>Activity Name</u>	<u>Description of Objective(s) with Reference to Specific output</u>	<u>MAIN Target Audience</u>	<u>Secondary Target Audience</u>
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Participation in the Annual meeting of the project	Participation in the Annual meeting of the project (Twitter)	Research communities	Industry, EU Institutions., civil society
CSIC	Dissemination	Conferences	FISHFORUM2024 Turkey	FISHFORUM2024 Turkey: Diversity, competition and collaboration in coastal fisheries	Regional authorities	EU Inst., Nat'l, Reg., and Local Auth., International Orgs.
CSIC	Dissemination	Education and training events	Science week organised by ICM-CSIC	Participation in the Science week organised by ICM-CSIC with an activity, in which we explained our main work related to different projects, including MarinePlan	Regional authorities	Civil Society, Citizens
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Participation in the Science week organised by ICM	Participation in the Science week organised by ICM-CSIC (Twitter)	Research communities	Civil Society, Citizens
CSIC	Dissemination	Education and training events	Course of EwE food web modelling organised by ICM	Host of the course of EwE food web modelling organised at the ICM-CSIC (MarinePlan also participating)	Research communities	EU Institutions, Civil Society, Citizens
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Participation in the course of EwE	Participation in the course of EwE food web modelling organised by ICM-CSIC (Twitter)	Research communities	EU Institutions., Civil Society, Citizens
CSIC	Dissemination	Education and training events	2 workshops conducted in different schools	2 workshops conducted in different schools presenting our main work related to different projects, including MarinePlan	Local authorities	Civil Society, Citizens

CSIC	Communication	Social media	Creation X channel of iMARES group (@iMARES_group)	Creation of our new X channel of iMARES group (@iMARES_group) where we are publishing all the main activities of the group, including those from MarinePlan project	Research communities	Industry, EU Institutions., Nat'l, Reg., and Local Authorities., Int'l Orgs., Civil Society, Citizens
AZTI	Dissemination	Education and training events	Placement in AZTI (under the supervision of I. Galparsoro) of a PhD student (Olga Lukyanova). She started the PhD at AZTI in June 2023	PhD on marine spatial planning and marine protected areas.	Research communities	
QUB	Dissemination	Conferences	13th Annual Marine Economics and Policy Research S	The 13th Annual Marine Economics and Policy Research Symposium on Wednesday 13th December 2023. This symposium was hosted by the University of Galway, in partnership with the Marine Institute of Ireland. At the symposium, QUB presented on issues relating to Deliverable 4.2 of MarinePlan. This involved a discussion of themes associated with knowledge use, production and communication, and how non-government actors and/or stakeholders engage with governance processes. In particular, a fisheries	Research communities	Local Authorities, Civil Society

				management network was used as a case study.		
SZN (and UAEGEAN)	Dissemination	Meetings	Seminar on the implementation of SDM for presence-	Seminar on the implementation of SDM for presence-only data	Research Communities	
UAEGEAN	Dissemination	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	LIFE MareNatura kick-off meeting	Participation in Kick-off Meeting of LIFE MareNatura where MarinePlan was presented as a key project producing valuable knowledge relevant to the objectives and study area of MareNatura.	Research Communities	National Authorities
UNINA	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	EU Blue Parks Community workshop	6 December 2023, 14:30 – 17:30 CET EU Blue Parks Community workshop 'Working together for the protection and restoration of marine ecosystems and biodiversity' (Participation of Simonetta to network & share results)	Research Communities	
UNINA (and SZN)	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	NBFC conference on biodiversity	Participation to the NBFC conference on biodiversity (Palermo 20-22 of May)	Research Communities	Industry, Innovators, Regional and Local Authorities, Citizens
IECS	Dissemination	Education and training events	Promoting MarinePlan research and scientific careers through training and PhD supervision	Webinar session on the topic of publishing, by Mike Elliott (see Task 6.10). Promoting MarinePlan research and scientific careers through training and PhD supervision	Research Communities	

IECS	Dissemination	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Collaboration between MSP4BIO project and MarinePlan project	Professor M. Elliott discussed the MarinePlan project at the Science Advisory Board of the sister-project MSP4BIO in its annual meetings in October and November 2023.	Research Communities	
IECS	Dissemination	Other scientific collaboration	Transferring MarinePlanS knowledge to Future Earth Coasts project CyberCoast	The Future Earth Coasts project CyberCoast, organized from China, was started in September 2023 with input from Professor Elliott based on MarinePlan and its subsequent meeting included an on-line presentation (on 20th October 2023) from Gemma Smith (IECS) 'Holism in Marine Management: An Integrated Systems Analysis Approach in Marine Social-Ecological Systems'. Transferring MarinePlan's knowledge to Future Earth Coasts project CyberCoast	Research Communities	
IECS	Dissemination	Conferences	Presentation of MarinePlan project at Shipping and Environment conference, Gothenburg	27-28th September Gothenburg – Shipping and Environment conference 2023: 'Managing Marine Resources Sustainably: a transdisciplinary approach to the causes, consequences and responses to environmental problems of shipping and navigation' presented by Michael Elliott and Ida-Maja Hassellöv (Chalmers Univ., Gothenburg).	Industry, Business Partners	

IECS	Dissemination	Education and training events	research seminar at Chalmers Univ., Gothenburg	29th September in a research seminar at Chalmers Univ., Gothenburg – Prof. Elliott presented ‘Defining priorities for science and management for the sustainable use of marine resources’.	Research communities	
IECS	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Collaboration between SEA-UNICORN COST-ACTION project and MarinePlan project	9-11th October 2023: SEA-UNICORN COST-ACTION MFC-MSP meeting Bremerhaven – ‘Marine natural and societal connectivity, coherence and equivalence for transboundary issues in relation to Systematic Conservation Planning and MSP’, presented by Michael Elliott, Roland Cormier and Angel Borja. Professor Elliott also mentioned the results of the project at the meetings on 30th October and 17th November 2023 for the SEA UNICORN project meeting. Collaboration between SEA-UNICORN COST-ACTION project and MarinePlan project	Research communities	
IECS	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Keynote presentation on MarinePlan at ICES WGCEAM meeting	23-25th October 2023 ICES WGCEAM (Working Group Cumulative Effects Assessment for Management) on line meeting – Professor Elliott gave a presentation on the ‘Background to Cumulative Effects/Impacts Assessment’. Keynote presentation on	Research communities	

				MarinePlan at ICES WGCEAM meeting		
IECS	Dissemination	Conferences	Transferring MarinePlan knowledge to the Future Earth Coasts initiative, China	6th November 2023 - Shanghai and on-line meeting for Future Earth Coasts – ‘MegaDelta Meeting Introduction’ presented by Professor Elliott using information from the project. Transferring MarinePlan knowledge to the Future Earth Coasts initiative, China	Research communities	Citizens
IECS	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Promotion of MarinePlan at the Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management	9-10th November 2023 Stockholm – Importance of Marine Environmental Monitoring for Sustainable Marine Management (MEMFIS) Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management – M. Elliott presented on ‘Coping with the marine environmental assessment paradox – increasing demands but with decreasing resources!’. Promotion of MarinePlan at the Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management	National Authorities	
IECS	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Promotion of MarinePlan at the HOPOPoP #1 International Meeting	14-16th November HOPOPoP #1 International Meeting - Marine protected areas as living labs: lessons learned and future perspective meeting Plouzané, France – re. marine planning M. Elliott presented ‘UK Marine Planning and Recent European Developments – Introduction’.	Research communities	

				Promotion of MarinePlan at the HOPOPoP #1 International Meeting		
IECS	Dissemination	Education and training events	Lecturing by Professor Elliott @Chester University	20th October Chester University – Lecturing by Professor Elliott to Postgraduates at Chester University, UK, on marine Environmental Impact Assessment. Promoting MarinePlan research and scientific careers through training and PhD supervision	Research communities	
AZTI	Dissemination	Education and training events	Placement in AZTI (under the supervision of I. Galparsoro) of a PhD student (Olga Lukyanova). She started the PhD at AZTI in June 2023	PhD on marine spatial planning and marine protected areas.	Research communities	
CSIC	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	UN OCEAN DECADE Conference.	Poster: Integrated marine ecosystem assessments to face Ocean Decade Challenges. Authors: Marta Coll, Francisco Ramírez, Maria Bas, Miquel Ortega, Àngela Olvera, Jeroen Steenbeek, Valerio Sbragaglia, Konstantina Agiadi	Research communities	EU Institutions., National, Regional and Local Authorities, Civil Society, Citizens
CSIC	Communication	Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	UN OCEAN DECADE Conference.	Poster: Integrated marine ecosystem assessments to face Ocean Decade Challenges. Authors: Marta Coll, Francisco Ramírez, Maria Bas, Miquel Ortega, Àngela Olvera, Jeroen	Research communities	EU Institutions, National, Regional and Local Authorities, Civil Society, Citizens

				Steenbeek, Valerio Sbragaglia, Konstantina Agiadi		
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Participation UN OCEAN DECADE Conference	Participation UN OCEAN DECADE Conference (Twitter)	Research communities	EU Inst., Nat'l, Regional and Local Authorities, Civil Society, Citizens, Int'l Orgs.
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Participation online in the Planning Sites Workshop	Participation online in the Planning Sites Workshop (Twitter)	Research communities	Industry Partners, EU Onst., Civil Society, citizens, Int'l Orgs.
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Participation in the Annual meeting of the project	Participation in the Annual meeting of the project (Twitter)	Research communities	Industry Partners, EU Onst., Civil Society, citizens, Int'l Orgs.
CSIC	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Ecopath 40 Years Conference	Poster: Assessing the effect of banning bottom trawling within Natura 2000 sites of the Habitat Directive in the Western Mediterranean Sea. Authors: Castro-Cadenas, M.D., Szalaj, D., Havlík, P., Augustynczik, A.L.D. Guéret, S., Bas M., Ortega, M., Steenbeek, J., Sbragaglia V., and Coll, M.	Research communities	Industry Partners, EU Onst., Civil Society, citizens, International Organizations.
CSIC	Communication	Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	Ecopath 40 Years Conference	Poster: Assessing the effect of banning bottom trawling within Natura 2000 sites of the Habitat Directive in the Western Mediterranean Sea. Authors: Castro-Cadenas, M.D., Szalaj, D., Havlík, P., Augustynczik, A.L.D. Guéret, S., Bas M., Ortega, M., Steenbeek, J., Sbragaglia V., and Coll, M.	Research communities	Industry Partners, EU Inst., Civil Society, citizens, International Organizations.

CSIC	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	ICES Annual Science Conference	<p>Presentation: A framework and tool for assessing ecosystem-based marine spatial planning. Authors: I. Galparsoro, N. Montero, G. Mandiola, I. Menchaca, Á. Borja, E. Fabbrizzi, M. Bas, W. Flannery, R. Mzungu Runya, S. Giakoumi, M. Kruse, B. McAteer, G. Piet, S. Frascchetti, T. Morato, S. Degraer, M. Elliott, S. Barnard, S. Katsanevakis, S. Neuenfeldt, O. Lukyanova, and V. Stelzenmüller</p>	Research communities	Innovators, EU Institutions., National, Regional and Local Auth., Research Communities, Specific End User Communities
AZTI	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	ICES Annual Science Conference	<p>Presentation: A framework and tool for assessing ecosystem-based marine spatial planning. Authors: I. Galparsoro, N. Montero, G. Mandiola, I. Menchaca, Á. Borja, E. Fabbrizzi, M. Bas, W. Flannery, R. Mzungu Runya, S. Giakoumi, M. Kruse, B. McAteer, G. Piet, S. Frascchetti, T. Morato, S. Degraer, M. Elliott, S. Barnard, S. Katsanevakis, S. Neuenfeldt, O. Lukyanova, and V. Stelzenmüller</p>	EU Institutions	Research Communities, Specific End User Communities
AZTI	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	XVIIIth International Symposium on Oceanography of the Bay of Biscay (ISOBAY 18)	<p>Presentation: A novel approach for ecosystem-based conservation planning in the Bay of Biscay. Authors: Lukyanova O., Pouso S., García-Barón I., Borja A., Galparsoro I.</p>	Research communities	Research Communities, Specific End User Communities

AZTI	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	XVIIIth International Symposium on Oceanography of the Bay of Biscay (ISOBAY 18)	Poster: Assessing ecosystem-based marine spatial planning in the Bay of Biscay. Authors: Galparsoro I., Montero N., Mandiola G., Menchaca I., Laroussinie O., Alloncle N., Jacob C., Cervera-Nuñez C., Campillos-Llanos M.	Research communities	Research Communities, Specific End User Communities
AZTI	Dissemination	Other	Internal workshop in AZTI's headquarters	Presentation: New approaches to conservation and marine spatial planning based on ecosystem-based management. Authors: Galparsoro I., Montero N., Mandiola G., Menchaca I., Lukyanova, O.	Research communities	
AZTI	Dissemination	Education and training events	Placement in AZTI (under the supervision of I. Galparsoro) of a PhD student (Virginia Morrejón) from the University of Dublin. Period May 2024 until November 2024	PhD on marine spatial planning, specialising in the distribution of human activities and environmental pressures.	Research communities	
AZTI	Dissemination	Other scientific collaboration	1-week visit of Robert Runya from Marine Institute to AZTI. May 2024	Strengthening the collaboration between AZTI and Marine Institute in the framework of MarinePlan	Research communities	
AZTI	Dissemination	Education and training events	Placement in AZTI (under the supervision of I. Galparsoro) of a PhD student (Vitor da Souza; October 2023 to July 2024).	PhD on marine spatial planning, specialising in the distribution of human activities and environmental pressures. Work title: Applying BBN to determine spatial relationships between	Research communities	

			Cooperation Agreement between the Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina (UFSC), Brazil and Fundación AZTI (AZTI), Spain.	maritime activities in the Southern Brazilian Shelf		
AZTI	Dissemination	Education and training events	Placement in AZTI (under the supervision of I. Galparsoro) of a PhD student (Andrea Mattia Pacifico) from the University of Salento – Lecce (Italy). May 2024 until November 2024	PhD methods and approaches to ensure the sustainable development of seas, aiming to balance ecosystem protection and human activities, thereby contributing to marine spatial planning	Research communities	
AZTI	Dissemination	Education and training events	Placement in AZTI (under the supervision of I. Galparsoro) of a PhD student (Olga Lukyanova). She started the PhD at AZTI in June 2023	PhD on marine spatial planning and marine protected areas.	Research communities	
Thuenen	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Presented MarinePlan Project at the 9th World Fisheries Congress, 3-7 March 2024 in Seattle, WA, USA. (Maren Kruse)	Presented MarinePlan project to congress attendees. Congress was organized through the World Council of Fisheries Societies with aim to exchange ideas and research related to fisheries science, industry, conservation and management. MarinePlan project was presented and discussed with delegates and directly relates to	Research communities	Industry Partners

				WP7 work and Objective #1 of project (Co-development with stakeholders)		
Thuenen (and AZTI)	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Vanessa Stelzenmüller and Ibon G. participated in a Technical Expert Group at the CINEA: European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) Technical Expert Group on Data for Maritime Spatial Planning Meeting. 13-14 March 2024.	Participation by MarinePlan members in the Expert Group directly relates to WP7 (communication and dissemination) as well as Objective #1 of project: co-development with Stakeholder	Research communities	
Thuenen	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Maren Kruse presented information on MarinePlan at the 7th International Conference on Marine Connectivity (Montpellier, France, 27-31 May, 2024)	The Conference brought together marine scientists and stakeholders from around the world at the aquarium of Montpellier (Planet Ocean) in the South of France, to share the latest advances in the study of marine connectivity and its use in public and international policies for the sustainable management of the Ocean and its resources. <Presenting MarinePlan project directly ties into WP2 and WP5, and also to Objective #3 of the MP project	Research communities	Industry Partners
Thuenen	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet	Vanessa S. presented information about MarinePlan at the ICES Annual Science Conference 2024,	Presenting MarinePlan at this conference ties directly to WP1 and WP5, as well as project Objectives 1 and 3.		

		debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	from 9-12 September 2024 in Gateshead UK		Research communities	
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